

CERTIFYING TRUST IN AI SYSTEMS

CERTIFICATION MEANS

WHY CERTIFICATION?

WHAT TO CERTIFY?

HOW TO BENEFIT?

WHO CERTIFIES?

WHO BENEFITS?

ROADMAP FOR ACTION

